

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SITUATION: SPREAD OF INFECTIOUS DISEASES

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Annotation: This article devoted to open the theme Epidemiological situation: Spread of Infectious Diseases and covers the latest data about main reason of spreading this diseases. Moreover, in the article simple ways of preventing and avoiding infectious diseases were noted.

Key words: *“morovich diseases”, epidemiologic situation, biostatistics, generalist focusing, lower respiratory, less-developed economies.*

There's a incredible assortment of irresistible infections, and at all times they were the most foes of man. History knows numerous cases of the obliterating

impacts of smallpox, torment, cholera, typhoid, loose bowels, measles, flu. No ponder irresistible disease is called “morovich diseases.” They are the most cause of perilous epidemiologic circumstance. The study of disease transmission comes from the Greek words epi meaning on or approximately, demos the common individuals, and ology meaning to ponder a certain subject. Truly at that point, the study of disease transmission is the think about of individuals. Be that as it may, these days we utilize other terms like humanism and demography to cover the ponder of individuals. Instep, we utilize the study of disease transmission to cruel the think about of maladies in individuals. In specific, the study of disease transmission is the think about of what causes infections, where, when and in whom maladies take put, and how we avoid or control them. When the study of disease transmission was being created, it was since of major flare-ups of irresistible illnesses as a rule among destitute individuals. Over time, there were fewer infectious disease outbreaks, and more people were dying from acute non-infectious diseases like heart disease and cancer. So, epidemiologists started studying these as well.

In the long run, the study of disease transmission extended to cover inveterate conditions such as diabetes and asthma. It moreover moved into the zones of mental wellbeing, quality of life, and how social components and destitution impact wellbeing. Disease transmission experts are wellbeing experts who have examined the study of disease transmission and open health. The study of disease transmission is more often than not instructed at the postgraduate level, with most disease transmission experts having an beginning undergrad degree in pharmaceutical or biostatistics (the ponder of insights connected to pharmaceutical). However, epidemiologists can come from a wide variety of disciplines such as nursing or psychology. Epidemiologists either become a specialist in a given area such as cancer epidemiology, or infectious disease

epidemiology, or become a generalist focusing more on epidemiological methods. Biostatistics is a slightly separate discipline in its own right, with much overlap with epidemiology, and many biostatisticians like myself are also epidemiologists.

Perhaps a good analogy is that medical doctors look after the health of individuals, whereas epidemiologists look after the health of a population. Deaths due to infectious diseases are still very common despite the huge progress in antibiotic and vaccine development. In fact, five infectious diseases account for 1 in 8 deaths globally. They are: lower respiratory tract infections (including [pneumonia](#)), diarrhoeal diseases, HIV, Malaria and Tuberculosis. For both Malaria and Tuberculosis there are currently major concerns about multiple drug resistance (in other words most treatments not being effective), and there are concerns especially in Africa and Asia about counterfeit drugs containing little or no active ingredients. So, although chronic diseases have overtaken infectious diseases as leading causes of death in developed countries, tackling infectious diseases is still vitally important in both developed and less-developed economies. These are the terms we use to describe the status of a disease within a population. The continuous presence of an infectious disease in a geographical location is called endemic. For example, there are many parts of the world where Malaria is endemic — it is always present and kills over 400,000 people each year.

An epidemic is the occurrence of a disease that is greater than that expected in the location region. For example, there is currently an epidemic of Ebola virus in Congo and Uganda which started in 2018. An outbreak is like an epidemic but is often used for a more limited geographic area. For example, there has recently been an outbreak of measles in Samoa. Finally, when the epidemic involves different countries and a large population it is called a *pandemic*. Formally, an infectious disease is an illness caused by the transmission of an *infectious agent*, or

its toxic products, from an infected animal, person or other reservoir, to a susceptible *host*. That sounds very formal, so we will break down the statement into some of its component parts. In epidemiology, we often describe disease transmission in terms of the infectious agent, the host, the environment and the vector. This is often put into a diagram called the epidemiological triangle. An infectious agent is a pathogen (an organism that causes disease). There are many types of pathogen including bacteria, viruses, rickettsia, fungi, protozoa, helminths, prions, and parasites. In the case of the current pandemic, it is the SARS-associated coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) that is the infectious agent or pathogen that causes the disease, while the disease itself is called COVID-19.

Coronavirus illness 2019 (COVID-19) could be a infectious illness caused by a infection, the severe acute respiratory disorder coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2). The primary known case was distinguished in Wuhan, China, in December 2019. The illness rapidly spread around the world, coming about within the COVID-19 widespread. The side effects of COVID 19 are variable but frequently incorporate fever, hack, cerebral pain, weariness, breathing challenges, misfortune of scent, and misfortune of taste. Indications may start one to fourteen days after presentation to the infection. At slightest a third of individuals who are tainted don't create recognizable indications. Of those who create indications discernible sufficient to be classified as patients, most (81%) create mellow to direct indications (up to gentle pneumonia), whereas 14% create extreme side effects (dyspnea, hypoxia, or more than 50% lung inclusion on imaging), and 5% create basic indications (respiratory disappointment, stun, or multiorgan brokenness). Older people are at a higher risk of developing severe symptoms. Some people continue to experience a range of effects ([long COVID](#)) for months after recovery, and damage to organs has been observed. Multi-year studies are underway to further investigate the long-term effects of the disease. [COVID-19](#)

[transmits](#) when infectious particles are breathed in or come into contact with the eyes, nose, or mouth. The risk is highest when people are in close proximity, but small [airborne](#) particles containing the virus can remain suspended in the air and travel over longer distances, particularly indoors. Transmission can also occur when people touch their eyes, nose or mouth after touching surfaces or objects that have been contaminated by the virus. People remain contagious for up to 20 days and can spread the virus even if they do not develop symptoms.

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that Despite the sanitary well-being, advances in modern medicine, it is naive to believe that humanity has conquered infectious diseases, and each of us is at risk. Now in a world of rampant epidemics – AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria, measles, Ebola, whooping cough, influenza, and other diseases. Infections are caused by microscopic organisms known as pathogens — bacteria, viruses, fungi, or parasites — that enter the body, multiply, and interfere with normal functions. Infectious diseases are a leading cause of illness and death in many places around the world. Certain people are under particular risk of getting infectious diseases, like those with underlying cardiac illnesses, oncology patients, or those who are taking immunosuppressive medications. For most healthy people, however, following a few basic principles can go a long way in helping to prevent infections. Not long ago, no one understood that infectious diseases were caused by tiny organisms that moved from person to person. Even now, although we know that microscopic living microbes cause disease, how they do so is not always obvious. But we do know that most microbes enter through openings in the body — our noses, mouths, ears, anuses, and genital passages. They can also be transmitted through our skin through insect or animal bites. The best way to prevent infections is to block pathogens from entering the body.

REFERENCES:

1. [medium.com>...epidemiology-and-infectious-diseases...](https://medium.com/...epidemiology-and-infectious-diseases...)
2. ["Symptoms of Coronavirus". U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention \(CDC\)](#). 13 May 2020. [Archived](#) from the original on 17 June 2020. Retrieved 18 June 2020.
3. Хакимовна Х. Х. О‘quvchilar jismoniy tarbiyasi tizimida qattish //barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali. – 2022. – С. 378-381
4. Рахимова Д. Ж. и др.Изменение состава микроэлементов у детей с хроническим расстройством питания первых двух лет жизни на фоне ОКИ //Научный аспект. –2020. –Т. 2. –№. 1. –С. 252-258.
5. Turakulov Jamshid, Honbuvi Hakimovna .Ceative activity of abu raikhan beruni and social outlook // Academic research in educational sciences. 2022. №3
6. Turakulov Jamshid, Honbuvi Hakimovna. CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF ABU RAIKHAN BERUNI AND SOCIAL OUTLOOK // Academic research in educational sciences. 2022. №3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/creative-activity-of-abu-raikhan-beruni-and-social-outlook> (дата обращения: 23.01.2023).
7. Zokir Bulyaev Zainab Naimova S,, Khurliman Kurbanova , Honbuvi Khakimova,Hygienic Assessment Of Emission Influence From A Chemical Plant On Population’s Household Conditions, WellBeing And Health
8. Рахимова Д,Аскарлова Н,Хакимова Х. Изменение состава микроэлементов у детей с хроническим расстройством питания первых двух лет жизни на фоне оки